

Effect of the spline region faces number in the polygonal design on the performance of the Titanium dental implants, an important matter we overlook.

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Abstract

Dental implants design features had been debated for a long period. Abutment implant indexing feature needs special attention as it is producing an important effect on the implant performance. We want to investigate some of the issues of these features. Although the findings are not significant, this feature should get more attention in the general frame of the biomechanical evaluation of the dental implant based upon objective criteria. The current paper is an introductory text to reveal the effect of the indexing feature sides number on the implant performance and the relationship of orientation of this feature to the performance of the implant.

Keywords: Dental Implant Design, Stiffness, Numerical Simulation, Titanium

1. Introduction

Implant-abutment unit had many regions. One of the important regions is the spline region of the implant. Spline region is a region of non-contact between the implant and the abutment where strain may cause a potent effect on the implant. There are many configurations that produce uneven regions or in another term lead to accumulation of stresses that even lead to fracture of the implant. It occurs between 2 regions of contacts between the abutment and the implant. Implant had many features (1) in the design and each feature had been purposed by the manufacturers

Figure 1 Different design reflects the engineering vision of the manufacturing companies

The implant abutment connection had 3 regions, we had called these regions as the **Hub and Shaft Region** (2)

- **Cone regions**
- **Spline region**
- **Connecting screw region**

Figure 2 The black box represents the implant abutment connection. The red outline represents the cone region. The green region represents the spline region which has indexing function. The yellow region represents the connecting screw vent inside the implant

Vast majority of the indexing features is of hexagonal shape. For less extent octagonal shape had been implemented. Many other regions had been manufactured also. Many companies manufacture this region from shapes other than the polygonal shape, but the popularities of these systems are not like the former.

We want to highlight the importance of considering this region of the performance of the dental implants as a passive region. Although it is not clear exactly to which extent the effects of the spline region on the short- and long-term performance of the implant. Short-term regarding the stress distribution and long-term regarding the fatigue and corrosion of the Titanium dental implants. (3)

In the current paper, we want to demonstrate the effect of the spline region on the implant as well as the effect of the direction force in relation to the spline orientation

Of course, when we choose the effect of the direction of the head of the rigid to the orientation of the spline faces of the mode, it should be compared to the two-piece implants without bone as the addition of the bone analogue will complicate the analysis. (4)

Figure 3 this model had threads. Our model is simpler to provide more easier analysis

In the previous model of two-piece tapered without bone, the face in the Y Direction was vertical to the surface of the implant's spline. We rotate the implant by an angle according to the no. of spline surfaces

As an example, if it has 8 sides, it should be rotated by $360 / 16 = 22.5$ degree. But after rotation of the implant and abutment by 22.5 degrees the first vertical to the angle present between the faces of the spline.

To demonstrate the effect of force application with the implant spline, we rotate implant and abutment by an angle of certain value according to the spline faces numbers. So, after rotation, the corner will be in the line of force

Figure 4 There are two regions red lines force direction to the angular region of the spline and blue lines force toward the flat region

Figure 5 It is an engineering axiom that the shaft and hub connection depend upon the geometrical configuration of both

Figure 6 Direct vs indirect wedging effect. In both models, some sort of sliding would occur at the inclined surfaces

Although we had represented the model in the detailed data set without clearance between the implant and the abutment, we had considered this space in the first data sets, the concise version. The variables that determine the stability of abutment to the implant are

- The taper of the abutment hub and shaft region, namely cone region
- The Spline configuration

Figure 7 the angle of rotation needed for each model is apparent here

Any inclined force has two components. With a decreased angle, the component B share will be lesser. When there is no spline (circular design) the resultant angle will be zero and the will no longer B components. When the angle decreases the meaning the share of the component of the force that will tend to be different from the previous larger angle.

Figure 8 Let's suppose that there's a circle of diameter 10 mm, its circumference will be = 31.4159mm

In the Figure 8 we can conclude

- If we fit a square inside it, its circumference will be = 28.28mm
- If we fit a hexagon inside it, its circumference will be =30mm
- If we fit an octagon inside it, its circumference will be = 30.64mm
- If we fit a hexadecagon inside it, its circumference will be = 31.2mm
- If we fit a triacontadigon inside it, its circumference will be = 31.36mm

So, with each increase, we will get closer and closer to the circle with its circumference which is 31.4159mm, this is associated with both direct and indirect wedging effect. In the model of a different number of sides of the spline of the shaft and hub region, we think that is there no need to represent the cutting plots of the first and third principal of both strain and stresses as well as the contour plots because the main concepts behind these clothes had been thoroughly explained and highlighted in the previous experiments. When the abutment had spline of more sides, it will be closer to the circle whenever the account of the sides increases. Besides, to increase the ability to get more abutment positions possibilities, especially in case of the angulated abutment (as all implant surgeons facing routinely), increasing the account of sides with the same major diameter of spline had the better effect of implant performance.

Figure 9 All the shapes have the same major diameter, but the minor diameter is different according to the sides no. the minor diameter of the triangle is about half of the major diameter.

The difference between the minor diameter of the 16 side's spline and the major diameter is subtle, which results in a lesser effect of the force direction in relation to the spline.

Figure 10 These are significant variations resulted between rotated and non-rotated in the case of 4 sided-spline in relation to the force direction in the case of four sides.

These variations, in the Figure 10, vanish gradually until reaching the circular model (which is a non-indexed implant). When the numbers of faces increase, the mass of the abutment will be increased as well. There will be a coincident decrease in the mass of the implant. The increase in the side number will result in more uniform abutment and implant response. This change in the stiffness should be observed.

Figure 11 dental bridge connector design affects the stiffness which in return affect the mechanical properties of the bridge

Figure 12 A suggest antirotating feature of the abutment

Figure 13 This is the indexing feature of the abutment at its lower surface which will face the deepest surface inside the implant (deepest surface inside the female portion of the hub and shaft region in case of internal connection between the implant and the abutment)

To reduce the effect of indexing, we suggest doing the indexing at the base of the abutment which could be associated with tapered or non-tapered abutment. We think this could better than the currently used indexing, as it provides uniform width of the vent of the hub and shaft region. Circular abutment model FEA study (with infinity walls spline) had not been done, although we want to include it in the next editions of this book IF Almighty Allah wants.

This design will also so have a very important anti-rotation as in case of some torque applied to the abutment to rotate it, will get the upward direction that will be faced by the connecting screw. This concept (what is called

Wedge-Lock Washers) had been applied successfully in mechanical engineering as part of prevention of screw loosening.

Methods

We had compared between these models

- Three sides which a design close to the design done or implemented by Noble BioCare
- 4 sides as in Bili implant
- 6 sides spline region as in the vast majority of the dental implant systems
- 8 sides spline region as in the JD oct and Mode dental implants
- 12 sides spline region as in IML implant
- Circular spline region

As we have totally different designs among the previous systems, we had made our own comparison model based on one of the Mohammed bodies

SolidWorks was used to synthesis the models and the testing environment was COMSOL Multiphysics.

As we are dealing with the connection only, we had chosen to test the design in the simplest way. The simplest way is to fix the button o the implant model. Universal holder or force applicator had been integrated with the upper part of the abutment. The results in this study and the next studies had 2 main benefits:

- Exposing how the fundamental parts of the design are working
- Establishment of objective comparison criteria
- Raising all the question in engineering ways to be answered by the manufacturing companies

Figure 14 The current comparison mainly between these designs

Figure 15 We had to modify the design of the 3 sides spline region to be in accordance with other criteria which is the screw hole

Figure 16 This is the implant model of the 3 sides spline. This modification of the 3 sides spline is apparent

Figure 17 4 sides spline variant

Figure 18 6 sides spline design variant

Figure 19 8 sides spline region

Rotation angles

- For 3 sides 60 degrees
- For 4 sides 45
- For 6 sides 30
- For 8 sides 22.5
- For the 12 sides it will be 15 degrees

At the end of the study, we had tried the cylindrical model. Although in the next papers we will answer many questions emerged here.

Simply, faces of the spline will affect positional ability of the implant and the stresses distribution

The positional indexing of the angled abutment which in the case of angulated abutment and the system had limited number of faces it will add a complicated step in the management that could put the dentist in a situation with poor prosthetic and unforgettable bitter taste of the clinical work.

In addition to that the lessening of the side number will obligate to provide unnecessary prosthetic number. It is wise to make thing easier and reduce number of the needed tools

Figure 20 In the case of 3 sides alpine you have only 3 positions of the angulated abutment which is totally unacceptable totally disturbing the restoration process in many instances

Figure 21 The 4 sides spline regions also impose considerable limitation. Although many manufacturers produce A and B abutments, but still a limiting feature. We here call it rotated and not rotated model

Figure 22 6 sides spline is a popular choice with accepted practicability due to its accepted range of indexing and resultant position ability

Figure 23 8 sides spline provide the best ability to fine tune the position of the angulated abutment especially in the case limited space in the anterior region

Figure 24 12 sides spline provide the best ability to fine tune the position of the angulated abutment especially in the case limited space in the anterior region

Figure 25 The ultimate freedom of choosing the position is in the circular spline region

Distribution of the stresses within the implant not the abutment as the abutment is off from contact due to the manufacturing clearances consideration

Figure 26 Among all the designs the cone region and the other regions of all implants are similar as well as the body of the implant. This also include the abutment and connecting screw submodels

In the Figure 26

- Volume of the 3 sides spline region 6.2827 mm^3
- Volume of the 4 sides spline region 6.2209 mm^3
- Volume of the 6 sides spline region 5.8727 mm^3
- Volume of the 8 sides spline region 5.7448 mm^3
- Volume of the 12 sides spline region 5.5382 mm^3
- Volume of the circular spline region 5.2898 mm^3

Figure 27 It is highly advisable to make the cone region of higher stiffness than the next region, namely spline region. This is called gradient of stiffness

The spline region of the implant. Spline region of the abutment had no significant issue on the performance of the implant due to the manufacturing clearances as we said. Even with sever loading cases that might lead to contact between the abutment and the implant, it still severs loading cases that need to reviewed in this context

Figure 28 Lateral load 100 newtons at the upper part are evident as well as and the fixed region on the bottom is also apparent

Results and discussions

We had 2 sets of the results

- Concise results had been done in the 2025
- Original detailed results writing in 2017

We invite the reader to read the first set and if he is interested in more results ha can proceed to read the other set

Figure 29 Comparison between how much involved strain energy in the model of the 3 sides spline region and the model of the 8 sides spline

Figure 30 Volume of the region with defined areas engaged with certain amount of strain energy density was :for the 8 sides spline the results = 9.6323 mm^3 and for 3 sides spline the results = 6.8915 mm^3

In the Figure 30 it is clearly apparent that this lead to more concentration of the strain energy density and affect plasticity response of the implant and the fatigue life on the long-term loading

Figure 31 The first model on the left is the rotated model and the model on the right represent the non-rotated model

There is a marked difference between the model and the rotated model. This should be held in the mind of any dentist who places an implant. This variable could not be totally attributed to the final loading condition of the prosthetic part.

Figure 32 Displacement of the 3 sides spline region

Figure 33 Cross section of the Displacement of the 3 sides spline region

Figure 34 Displacement of the 3 sides spline region only the implant

Figure 35 Von mises stress cross section of the 3 sides spline region

Figure 36 Displacement of the rotated 3 sides spline model

Figure 38 Displacement of the rotated 3 sides spline region only the implant

Figure 39 Von mises stress cross section of the rotated 3 sides spline region

Figure 40 The model on the left represents the non-rotated model and the model on the right represent the rotated model

Figure 41 Displacement of the 4 sides spline

Figure 43 Displacement of the only implant 4 sides spline

Figure 44 Cross section of the 4 sides splines Von Mises stress

Figure 45 Displacement of the rotated 4 sides spline model

Figure 46 Displacement of the rotated 4 sides spline model

Figure 47 Displacement of the rotated 4 sides spline model only the implant

Figure 48 Cross section of the rotated 4 sides von mises stress

Figure 49 The model on the left represents the non-rotated model and that on the right represent the rotated model. The difference between the 6 sides spline and 4 sides spline is apparent

Figure 50 6 sides spline displacement

Figure 51 Cross section of the 6 sides spline displacement

Figure 52 6 sides displacement only the implant

Figure 53 6 sides spline cross section for von mises stress

Figure 54 Rotated 6 spline model displacement

Figure 55 Rotated 6 sides spline displacement

Figure 56 Rotated 6 side spline only implant displacement

Figure 57 rotated 6 sides spline von mises stress

Figure 58 The model on the right represents the non-rotated model and the model on the left represent the rotated model

Figure 59 8 sides spline displacement

Figure 60 8 sides spline cross section displacement

Figure 61 8 sides spline displacement only the implant

Figure 62 8 sides spline von mises cross section

Figure 63 Rotated 8 side spline displacement

Figure 64 Rotated 8 side spline cross section displacement

Figure 65 Rotated 8 side spline displacement only the implant

Figure 66 Rotated 8 side spline von mises stress

All non-rotated model had force perpendicular on one of the faces, while in the rotated models, the force vector will bisect the one of the angles of the spline region. No intermediary angle had been tested.

The dilemma of the dimensions remains an area that need more investigations

In this paper we want to investigate the main concept needed for evaluation

Side numbers	Maximum total displacement at abutment	Maximum displacement at the implant	Difference between rotated and non-rotated models	Ratio of the abutment implant displacement (gradient of the stiffness)
3 sides	0.5024	0.1131	0.0742	4.442
Rotated 3 sides	0.5766	0.112	Rotated higher	5.148
4sides	0.5682	0.1178	0.0681	4.823
Rotated 4 sides	0.5001	0.113	Rotated lower	4.425
6 sides	0.5248	0.1135	0.1064	4.623
Rotated 6 sides	0.6312	0.1193	Rotated higher	5.290
8 sides	0.5905	0.1199	0.0336	4.924
Rotated 8 sides	0.6241	0.1232	Rotated higher	5.065
12 sides	0.6126	0.1205	0.1096	5.083
Rotated 12 sides	0.503	0.1142	Rotated lower	4.404
Circular spline region (no feature)	0.6431	0.1177	It is circular	5.463

- 3 sides and 4 sides could not be compared or correlated directly to the other model as they had maximum amount of deviation from the polygonicity.
- The difference between the displacement had been reduced with the increase of the face numbers in certain range and return to get another pattern of change.
- We had not tried side number more than 12, although this is highly advisable.
- Ration of the total displacement at the abutment to that in implant displacement (gradient of the stiffness) reflects the stiffness at the connection region, which should be get our priority in the design process
- With the increase in the number of faces, the more uniformity of the stiffness is attained as we are getting closer to the circular design
- The balance between stiffness and the design should be attained carefully

Figure 67 This is the 8 sides spline region in rotated and non-rotated model

The closer they get to each other the better result but the mass effect should be calculated wisely.

Figure 68 Von mises stress of the 3 sides spline. In the next paper we will give more space for the discussion of the stress's distribution within the implant and abutments domains

Detailed set of results

Slice: Second principal strain (1)

Figure 942

The spline could be ranged from triangular-shaped (just three sides) to circular (infinity faces) according to the side numbers

1 From figure 1 to figure 6 the force vector is bisecting one of the angles of the 4 sided spline

From figure 7 to figure 12 the force vector is perpendicular to one of the walls of the 4 sided spline

From figure 15 to figure 17 the force vector is bisecting one of the angles of the 6 sided spline

From figure 18 to figure 20 the force vector is perpendicular to one of the walls of 6 sided spline

From figure 23 to figure 27 the force vector is bisecting one of the angles of the 8 sided spline

From figure 28 to figure 32 the force vector is perpendicular to one of the walls of 8 sided spline

From figure 33 to figure 38 the force vector is bisecting one of the angles of the 16 sided spline

From figure 39 to figure 44 the force vector is perpendicular to one of the walls of 16 sided spline

From figure 45 to figure 49 the force vector is bisecting one of the angles of the 32 sided spline
From figure 50 to figure 56 the force vector is perpendicular to one of the walls of 32 sided spline

The index cross-section could be any design and to simplify the effect of spline geometrical configuration in the implant performance we have to do this study. The addition of bone block to the study will complicate the performance and as well as the addition of any feature (threads or fins).

The Region at the side of force application is totally different from the other model, this is especially significant at region A which is corresponding to the spline region of the implant, where the male spline of the abutment is residing in the female spline of the implant

This reciprocation is very limited at 32 sides indexed spline

Slice: Second principal stress (N/m²)

Figure 943

The contrast between the two models is less significant

Figure 944

In all models, there are direct or indirect wedge effects

The four-sided spline of the hub and shaft region is the only model that has no wedge effect

Difference between the two models decreases with the increase in sides number, which indicates more predictable uniform stress and strain distribution whatever the direction of the force is

Direct vs indirect wedging effect

In both models, some sort of

Sliding would occur at the inclined surfaces

Let's suppose that there's a circle of diameter 10 mm, its circumference will be = 31.4159mm

If we fit a square inside it, its circumference will be = 28.28mm

If we fit a hexagon inside it, its circumference will be =30mm

If we fit an octagon inside it, its circumference will be = 30.64mm

If we fit a hexadecagon inside it, its circumference will be = 31.2mm

If we fit a triacontadigon inside it, its circumference will be = 31.36mm

So with each increase, we will get closer and closer to the circle with its circumference which is 31.4159mm, this is associated with both direct and indirect wedging effect

Figure 945

The area A would be more prone to strain and stresses

The T' in the best situation will remain less than T (this difference will reduce with increase in the sides numbers)

So if the T' have least value (when the force direction is perpendicular on one of the walls of the spline of the hub and shaft region) index deformity would occur

C & C' will remain constant

So if we manipulate the spline sides count, that means we could lessen the effect of the force when its vector is in the less favorable direction

In case of constant T : T' the better distribution of stress even over the region of C C'

We cannot determine what is the best direction of the spline for a certain pattern

Increase the spline walls number had other advantages in providing more indexing to the abutment which is of indispensable benefit especially when the abutment is used

Figure 946

Distribution of strain energy density is different between the two models, but each model began to be closer to other with the increase in the faces number

Slice: Volumetric strain (1)

Figure 947

When the force applied perpendicular to one of the faces of the spline of hub and shaft region, the strain is more in the implant, less in the abutment and vice versa,(when the force is bisecting one of the spline angles)

Slice: Second principal strain (1)

Figure 948

Slice: Second principal stress (N/m²)

Figure 949

Figure 950

Figure 951

Figure 952

Slice: Volumetric strain (1)

Figure 953

Slice: Volumetric strain (1)

Figure 954

Slice: Second principal stress (N/m²)

Figure 955

Figure 956

Figure 957

Slice: Volumetric strain (1)

Figure 958

Slice: Second principal strain (1)

Figure 959

Figure 960

Figure 961

Figure 962

Slice: Volumetric strain (1)

Figure 963

Slice: Second principal strain (1)

Figure 964

Slice: Second principal stress (N/m²)

Figure 965

Figure 966

Figure 967

Slice: Elastic strain energy density (J/m³)

Figure 968

Slice: Second principal strain (1)

Figure 969

Slice: Second principal stress (N/m²)

Figure 970

Figure 971

Figure 972

Slice: Elastic strain energy density (J/m³)

Figure 973

Slice: Second principal strain (1)

Figure 974

Slice: Second principal stress (J/m³)

Figure 975

Figure 976

Figure 977

Slice: Elastic strain energy density (J/m³)

Figure 978

Slice: Volumetric strain (1)

Figure 979

Slice: Second principal strain (1)

Figure 980

Slice: Second principal stress (J/m³)

Figure 981

Slice: Total displacement (m)

Figure 982

Figure 983

Slice: Elastic strain energy density (J/m³)

Figure 984

Slice: Volumetric strain (1)

Figure 985

Slice: Second principal strain (1)

Figure 986

Figure 987

Figure 988

Figure 989

Slice: Elastic strain energy density (N/m²)

Figure 990

Slice: Volumetric strain (1)

Figure 991

Slice: Second principal strain (1)

Figure 992

Slice: Second principal stress (N/m²)

Figure 993

Figure 994

Figure 995

Slice: Elastic strain energy density (N/m²)

Figure 996

Slice: Volumetric strain (1)

Figure 997

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